

Urban Meta Museum

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ABSTRACT: Urban public spaces are an ideal field for investigation on how digital and physical can coexist concur, interact, intermingle and co-generate a new hybrid and augmented reality. Digital spheres mixed with the physical, material surroundings, create association, amplification, multiplicity and diversification, alongside with the possibility of constant re-interpretation and meta-production.

The city historically has been an open laboratory of meta-production and overlapping layering that sometimes cover and perhaps erase previous layers, or in other cases leave them in a pending state constructing a palimpsest that reveals the vertical time organization of the city in different, successive layers.

PALIMPSEST is a program funded by GRIT INTERREG, Priority Axis 2 - Integrated Environmental Management that works on the concept of the city's palimpsest and the potential that digital technologies provide to recuperate lost or forgotten layers of the city. PALIMPSEST rethinks concepts such as the Archive and the Museum that are transformed by the post-alphabetic era and redesigns their novel, fluid, participatory and interconnected version. The main aim is to revitalize the city's palimpsest by incorporating forgotten events and stories that took place in the city's urban web. This way , PALIMPSEST will activate an open and editable archive in the form of an app and an open, immaterial museum that embeds art installations and organizes an extra stratification in the city.

Content for the PALIMPSEST museum is co-created by the public involved in the collection of narratives from the city's past and artists responsible for the mise en scène of the narratives in the public urban space. This interrelation of experts and public, of traditional emitters and receivers, of authors and audience for the co-creation and the common authorship of the content is an issue of great significance. Architects are re-positioned as mediators that inter-relate people, stories, art and the city.

KEYWORDS: urban, museum, meta-production, palimpsest, art-installations

1. INTRODUCTION

The proliferation of digital technologies introduces the post-alphabetic era, an era of fusion and hybrids, where categories and typologies succumb to the fluidity and indefiniteness of a rapidly changing and uncertain world. Hybrids thrive in different aspects of contemporary life, while the digital and physical tend to merge and define augmented, mixed, hybrid realities. The post-alphabetic era, defined by the use of electronic media, comes after the alphabetic, defined by the predominance of the alphabet and vision and actually, doesn't seem to be closer to the pre-alphabetic, defined by orality and hearing, in contrast with what McLuhan had foreseen. The post-alphabetic era is a mixture of both the previous two phases and endorses hybrids. (Mantzou 2017)

In architecture the change is occurring in a rather vague and abstruse way, not as a result of a planned variation in prerequisites and criteria but rather as an intrinsic and bottom up transformation. Traditional architectural typologies gradually become obsolete as digital media merge time and space use. Public

and private spaces are mingled; working and home time is fused; commerce, entertainment, education and work are becoming impossible to distinguish.

Specifically, there are two typologies of interest for the present analysis. On one hand a concrete and regularized architectural typology, the museum, and on the other a rather fluid and difficult to capture but still distinct and clear category, the public space.

The museum typology is the ideal typology of the alphabetic world; a typology of taxonomy, hierarchy, surveillance and control. In the post-alphabetic word surveillance is traded for immersion and thus, the museum is being transformed by the urge to be appealing, all-encompassing and inclusive, to offer more and find new ways to engage the over-stimulated visitors. To do so the museum has to involve visitors and invite them to be more active and ideally to even post-produce and participate (Bourriaud 2006). Museums are adapting to change in a rather unsettled and spasmodic way by including commerce, entertainment and gaming in order to preserve and attract a more demanding and more saturated public. The past typology of the museum, a mechanism of surveillance, is now becoming an undetermined hybrid.

Public space is also under transformation; it is infiltrating previously considered private spheres and at the same time in its traditional form, that is as open, urban public space, it is being infiltrated by private spheres. Therefore, its borders are becoming indiscernible. Moreover, the public urban space of the city is compelled to offer more in order to compete with the digital public spheres and preserve its attractiveness in everyday life. In addition to its traditional fusion of uses, public space is now required to become more playful, engaging, interactive and interesting, in order to appeal to its digitally-awaken and maybe even spoiled users. The current public of public spaces demands an active role as central features and post-producers, constantly manipulating and interchanging information.

The case study presented is an ongoing GRIT Interreg EU program, PALIMPSEST, where Museum and Urban Public space are coalesced; where past and present coexist; where actors and public are interchangeable; where fiction and reality are fused. PALIMPSEST offers a test-bed for rethinking and reshaping from an architectural point of view previously distinct typologies, categories and organizations, such as the Museum and the Public space. At the same time, PALIMPSEST introduces practices where scientific, social, economic and marketing factors are integrated in order to create a holistic strategic approach. PALIMPSEST's midway results are presented as a temporary assessment of open-ended and inconclusive but yet indicative and suggestive outcomes that can be sufficient for further analysis and tactical suppositions.

2. DESCRIPTION

PALIMPSEST, is a program, funded by GRIT INTERREG, Priority Axis 2 - Integrated Environmental Management, which works upon cultural heritage and reshapes it for the digital age, by applying the concept and metaphor of the city as a palimpsest. Cultural Heritage constitutes one of the city's most valuable elements and assets, as it provides the subject with the opportunity to relate to the urban space and reactivate and reinforce its sense of historical, spatial and temporal continuity as well as the feeling of community and belonging. Digital technologies open a whole new field of actions for reintroducing cultural heritage into urban public space with their immense potential for archiving, processing, circulating and transforming /post-producing cultural heritage assets.

PALIMPSEST reconsiders concepts such as the Archive and the Museum with the intention of reconsidering them, by embracing their fluid, participatory and bottom-up, contemporary version. The intention is to reactivate and revitalize the city's palimpsest by incorporating forgotten events, stories and legends that allegedly took place in the city's urban web.

The narratives are retrieved as part of an oral history and tradition and transformed into an open, common and editable archive and a public, interactive, multisensorial and immaterial museum. The Museum and its archive are both post-productions that constitute an extra stratification in the city's public space, augmenting and hybridizing it.

The project's first stage involves an initial archive, created with the participation of schools and trans-generational collaboration. Students seek stories and memories related to the urban fabric of the city, from elder people in their familiar environment. They transcribe them, guiding the narrators to points that interest them and they tag, categorize and archive them. Tags used related to content are partly defined freely by the students and partly by the selection from a given tank of tags; while at the same time chronological and locative tags are also requested. Media used to record the stories are chosen by the students but must include text.

Subsequently the collected material is uploaded on a digital application open for the public. The users can search for stories and events using filters; can add stories following a similar procedure; can add comments to stories that already exist; and can suggest links among stories. This archive has all the features of a post-alphabetic archive, that is, a hybrid archive, which combines top-down rules and pre-existing structure with bottom-up, unrestricted and unforeseen development.

On one hand, it is configured with predetermined tags and temporal periods that users apply in order to categorize the stories that they upload or search the archive; on the other hand the stories that are presented are interpreted by the users who may add relevant audiovisual material, tag and also connect stories to other stories. Moderators, whose role is to check the posted material and its relevance, are, at first, members of the PALIMPSEST team and will gradually be substituted by active groups of the community that are already organizing similar collections of digital material. PALIMPSEST expects to create a community of involved moderators through the active engagement and participation of the public with the project. This community will act as guardians and trustees guaranteeing the proper functioning of the APP and its content, taking into consideration the reports and suggestions from the APP's users.

During the next stage, PALIMPSEST focuses on the creation of art installations in the urban space of the city. At first, the artists will select stories from the archive and then they will reinsert them as art installations in the city's public space appending them to their original location. The art installations will not significantly affect the physical condition of the city at its present condition. These settings, activated by visitors, will be interactive and multi-sensory, with no visible footprint in the urban area.

3. INNOVATION

PALIMPSEST proposes an open-air, constantly changing, evanescent, dreamlike, and yet, personalized, museistic experience that questions and defies traditional organizations of museums. As a Museum, PALIMPSEST is quite different than traditional museums in various levels, because it changes 1) the way content is provided 2), the fixed ubication in a building 3) the passive experience of the exhibits 4) the traditional bisection between curators and spectators 5) the detachment between exhibit and context.

Content is a novelty in PALIMPSEST. The PALIMPSEST's museum is co-created by both, the public involved in the collection of narratives from the city's past and also, artists responsible for the mise-en-scène of the narratives in the public urban space. The traditional, top-down, hierarchical structure of the conventional museum is reshaped as PALIMPSEST proposes a bottom up, participatory approximation through the interrelation of experts/actors and public, of traditional emitters and receivers, of authors and audience for the co-creation and common authorship of the content.

PALIMPSEST adopts the way information is produced in our current condition. In the post-alphabetic era receiving, producing, post-producing and emitting information becomes feasible for all those who use digital media. In our alphabetic past, information and knowledge were produced by certain centers and was distributed to the public that was usually a passive receiver. Authority was defined in advance and authorship remained indisputable. History, in the alphabetic world, was rendered as objective and could difficultly be perceived as an interpretative and biased understanding of the past. It claimed the right to be unique and impartial; the unbigoted and uncontestable knowledge of the past.

In this circumstance the museum enters a crisis as an authoritative and trustworthy institution for the objective and established representation of the world (Marotta 2012); as a hierarchical structure that

separates authors and public. This is the theoretical context upon which PALIMPSEST aims to work. One of its main objectives is to re-engage the inhabitants of the city, who are asked to collect, organize and associate, and therefore interpret information and narratives about the city's past. It is centered in the non-institutional history of the city, which is gathered through individual implication in the form of particular descriptions and subjective storytelling. The representation of the city in the MAP and APP format recreates the layered representation of the actual palimpsest, which every city has as a base, although it is often ignored and forgotten.

The Museum is not only dissolved as a top-down institution but also as an institution instituted in a separate, detached place. It becomes an open, overlapping and infiltrating structure that inhabits the context of its exhibits instead of isolating and disconnecting them from their milieu. The proposed model is one of a Museum without walls and limits; without predefined and fixed routes; without detachment, distance and disconnection. A hybrid condition of public urban space and museum that interact and infiltrate each other.

Consequently, the reactivation of the city's palimpsest changes the inhabitants' mental representation of the urban public space. Collected stories are elaborated and a number of them are selected by the artists as a basis for the construction of art installations in the city. The art installations take one-step further the interpretation of the collected stories. Their apparently random activation by visitors and the personalized perception of the museum that this creates, is an additional filter that distorts any possibility of an objective and hierarchical reading of the museum's content. PALIMPSEST rethinks the traditional classifications of authors and public without dissolving them. Oral history and collective cultural production which comes from our distant pre-alphabetic past coexist with the necessity of the artist as a distinct and established figure allowing both ends to explore and exploit the possibilities that arise from their interconnection.

PALIMPSEST regards the city's public open space as a canvas that is restored and recuperated and at the same time augmented and activated. It creates a hybrid approximation between the situationists' views for a city animated by its inhabitants and a more commercial, thematic approach, where the city is transformed in a spectacle structure (Debord 1967). Public space in this animated, augmented version offers possibilities for encounters and concurrences and engages passive and indifferent people to act and to experience vivid reinterpretations of past events instituted in their original place and transported in the present.

4. METHODOLOGY

PALIMPSEST, is a test-bed for theories and concepts with diverse origins, joined and blended together. It draws concepts and approaches from urban studies, museology, art and art theory, archiving, history cultural and media studies, informatics and digital cultural heritage, performance and staging and it is based on combinations and interactions. Methodologically PALIMPSEST is a hybrid; of different fields, of distinct categories, of diverse typologies. Therefore, although its methodology is constantly being elaborated and reconsidered it is arduous and impractical to present as is habitually done in predefined, hierarchical, controlled projects. The project is also a hybrid of top-down traditional organization and bottom-up, participatory approaches. Therefore, during its implementation and because of the genuine and profound interaction with agents and actors exterior to the project, the methodology is continuously reviewed and re-adapted.

Still, the PALIMPSEST stands for Post-Alphabetic, Interactive Museum using Participatory, Space-Embedded Story-Telling; these concepts are the principal basis for the PALIMPSEST's approach.

4.1. Post-Alphabetic

Post-alphabetic is the term McLuhan used to define the change that digital media would bring to our understanding, interrelation and mental construction of the world (McLuhan 1962). Decades after McLuhan's prophetic writings the post-alphabetic era is presented as an era where definitions, limits, categories, taxonomies, typologies and hierarchies succumb to the proliferation of mixtures, combinations, fluidity and hybrids. PALIMPSEST is post-alphabetic because it opts for mixing rather

than separating, it prefers merging rather than detaching; it is post-alphabetic because it acknowledges subjective and multiple truths as more powerful and reasonable than a unique and objective truth; it is post-alphabetic because it engages experts from multiple fields with the general public in the co-creation of a common, shared construction.

4.2. Space-Embedded

PALIMPSEST will not be strictly limited within an exhibition space. On the contrary it's content will be scattered all over the involved cities' historical centers and embedded in public spaces. The artworks and installations will be inspired by urban legends and old stories, so each and every artwork's identity will be inseparable from its physical location and surroundings. PALIMPSEST aims to re-install local lore into real-world environments, and by that old stories reclaim their rightful spaces.

When the project is fully developed, the art installations will be embedded in public spaces and will only become visible if the user activates them. This will give the ability to the public to experience urban legends where they originally took place. The merging of past and present worlds will redefine the urban experience and have both visitors and inhabitants look at mundane and common places differently. These artworks and installations may be digital and intangible, but they are embedded in physical, material spaces. The stories may have happened in the distant past, but they are restored to their former glory in the present. This hybrid museum experience opens up new possibilities that are yet to be explored. Dull places are now transformed into immersive, interactive encounters.

4.3. Augmented

Augmenting the public urban space of the city with interactive art installations, allows many levels of augmentations to occur. Past is added to the present as past stories return to their original location without affecting or altering it. Multisensorial art installations augment the perception of public space by creating a theatrical but still transient atmosphere that involves a holistic, somatic experience. The visitor is surrounded and not placed before the installations and becomes the center of the story told instead of a simple spectator. Everyday urban life is augmented by art installations that intensify and enhance our relation to it. The overwhelmed by digital media subject is satisfied by the multi-layering and the augmentation of the public space and becomes engaged and activated.

4.4. Participatory

PALIMPSEST introduces a groundbreaking, participatory museum experience, where the public can actively participate and shape the content exhibited. Users will be encouraged to download the app and upload forgotten tales, tag them and illustrate them with photos of family heirlooms, 3d models of historical objects, etc. Users will be able not just to share his/hers content, but also to shape the preexisting by creating connections and therefore, add another layer of history in the city's palimpsest. The tags that the user will select for each story will be based upon the repository of tags proposed by the students for the initial stories, used as a basis when launching the APP to the public. This repository of tags proposed by the students was further processed and analyzed by the PALIMPSEST Team in order to summarize and cover as much as possible of the vast range of the stories' thematics. The public's involvement is crucial for the project; the project is not about passive consumption, but active participation and the public, supported by experts, becomes the project's curator and trustee.

PALIMPSEST creates a spectacle that everyone can enjoy and, at the same time, it creates a situation where the visitor is not just a passive recipient but an inter-active participant. As a result, when it comes to our relationship with the city, the project's museum experience is a hybrid between spectacle/ theme entertainment practices and art-driven/ situationist approaches.

4.5. Interactive

Interaction is designed in different levels. On one hand, the APP that is being developed generates interactive content – an APP designed to involve the user and invite his/hers input but also respond to his/hers actions, capturing attention right from the start. When PALIMPSEST is fully developed, everyone will be able to download the APP and immerse oneself in art installations that will be waiting in public areas. These installations will also be interactive. They will only be activated by active human agents that will engage with them, explore their content and they will respond to their presence

accordingly. Users will not be able to activate the installations repeatedly because this would deconstruct the efforts to create an atmospheric dreamlike condition. Installations will interact intelligently with the public and will prioritize responses in different conditions following their programming.

4.6. Storytelling

PALIMPSEST is not concerned about historic truths – it is intrigued by orality and aims to preserve urban legends and stories. Local lore should be passed on and shared, because stories create a sense of community. PALIMPSEST helps people come together in a creative context while they delve into storytelling, a craft that is as old as time. The project aims to re-engage urban inhabitants and encourage them to collect and organize – or, in other words, interpret – information about the involved cities' past. At the same time, visitors can listen to other people's stories and uncover lost layers of the cities' past. This offers a possibility to strengthen the connection among past and future generations through sharing common experiences.

4.7 Museum

Museums are institutions that belong to the previous paradigm; the alphabetic, supervised, ordered and categorised world. In our days, the rapid information flows and the proliferation of channels that distribute it, leave no time to check it and assimilate it and therefore the reception becomes more passive. Supervision, classifications and categories soon became a thing of the past as we became accustomed to sometimes absurd, vivid collages and medleys with no hierarchical or taxonomical organization. Television ages gave the first stroke to the alphabetic hierarchical organization of facts that the printed book and the press had established (Debray 1992) and later on, the post-alphabetic media made each receiver a potential transmitter; leading us now to the point where information is produced and transmitted by all. This democratization process with the subsequent elimination of any truth-factor, previously idealized by the alphabetic, modern condition, is a deal-breaker for every authoritative and top-down construction. Instituted knowledge becomes disputed; sources are overwhelmingly multiplied and mostly uncontrollable; authorship is no longer a privileged condition of the few; selection, categorization, ordering and hierarchies appear in multiple versions, subjective and subjected to their transmitters.

The Museum is transformed in this post-alphabetical phase into an open basis, where each visitor can interact to create personal interpretations, interactions, narratives, in a digitally enhanced spatial context. The curator's authority as a specialist who oversees and controls the Museum cannot resist the pressure exerted by the digital sphere, as is the case with the creator's authority. The Museum becomes less hierarchical and rigorous, more anarchic and open but at the same time more spectacular and commercial. Digital reproduction as well as continuous post-production introduce new questions to the visitor-exhibit relationship that obviously affect the context of this relationship, namely the Museum. However, not everything is so transparent and clear. Similarly to what happens with the archive, in the museum too there are mechanisms that are often obscure and affect what is accessible and what remains missing. (Mantzou 2017)

5. OPEN CHALLENGES

PALIMPSEST as an ongoing project faces various open challenges that demand constant awareness and the ability to re-adjust and re-approach planning, without losing focus or lowering the quality of the final outcome.

First of all, one of the main challenges that PALIMPSEST has to deal with is the fruitful collaboration and effective cooperation of the project's multidisciplinary team, formed with members from different fields of study. Installation artists, architects, computer engineers and educators have to work closely together, go beyond their area of expertise and, at the same time, bring along their particular vision in the project. This multidisciplinary group has to combine those who have the know-how and those who know-what and have to apply this know-how in order to realize it, exchange methodologies and working procedures, thus giving the opportunity to re-think and re-invent processes, optimizing the final outcome. As a result, the configuration of an open-ended, authentically hybrid approach, where collaboration is not based neither in entirely discretizing tasks and responsibilities nor in totally mingling them, but rather

in finding ways to create perversion without dissolution was of vital importance. Collaborating closely as a group and organizing weekly meetings and periodical workshops has enabled satisfactory communication and complementary work.

Another challenge is the bottom-up, participatory character of the project because open access in the APP may also present issues of content control, which cannot be tackled easily and may undermine the accessibility and the openness of the database. The engagement of students and schools that have worked enthusiastically with the PALIMPSEST team has provided the project with many local agents willing to undertake a significant role as moderators of the APP.

At the same time, as the project is getting completed, maintenance issues arise and have to be tackled in order to assure the project's future. In order to address maintenance not just as repair and continuance of the project's function but also as a process of evolving and further developing, it is important to involve the local government but also other local public institutions and the local private sector. As a Museum PALIMPSEST aims to constantly renew its collection; and as a common, participatory project it intends to do so with the collaboration of different forms of local actors that share the same interest for the public urban common space of the city.

REFERENCES

- Bourriaud, N. 2006 *Postproduction*. Berlin: Sternberg Press
- Debord, G. 1967. *La Société du Spectacle*. Paris: Buchet-Chastel
- Debray, R. 1992. *Vie et mort de l'image. Une histoire du regard en Occident*. Paris: Gallimard Education
- Mantzou, P. 2017. *Aporia in Architecture: What now?*. Athens: Epikentron Publishers
- Marotta, A. 2012. *Typology: Museums in The Architectural Review*, December 2012
- McLuhan, M. 1962. *The Gutenberg Galaxy: The Making of Typographic Man*. Toronto: University of Toronto Press